

Repeatability of a primary thermometer and calibration of resistance thermometers between 5 K and 25 K at the sub-millikelvin level

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Abstract

In this work, improvements were made to our Single Pressure Refractive-Index Gas Thermometry (SPRIGT) system [[Metrologia 57 \(2020\) 065006](#)], whereas new experimental procedure of Constant Refractive-Index Gas Thermometry (CRIGT) was designed and implemented, and new values of $T-T_{90}$ obtained from 5 K to 25 K, 2.5 years after the first ones. Comparison results indicate our SPRIGT system is robust with excellent repeatability, reliability, and stability. Not only is the uncertainty in thermodynamic temperature T still below 0.17 mK, but also good reproducibility of T_{90} (temperature of the 1990 International Temperature Scale), T and $T-T_{90}$ is observed with values of the latter of 21 μ K, 28 μ K and 35 μ K respectively. Furthermore, we have firstly implemented direct disseminations of thermodynamic temperature T by establishing our own thermodynamic temperature wire scale under the new International System of Units (SI) from 5 K to 25 K. The remarkable agreement further enhances our confidence on SPRIGT for implementing the redefined kelvin below 25 K, disseminating thermodynamic temperature T , and ultimately partaking in an international comparison of thermodynamic temperature via highly stable resistance thermometers.

Keywords: Single pressure refractive index gas thermometry, thermodynamic temperature, wire temperature scale, virial coefficients, thermal stability

1 Introduction

In the recent past, following the 2019 re-definition of the kelvin in terms of a fixed value of the Boltzmann constant as part of the new International System of Units (SI), measurements of the $T-T_{90}$ (the discrepancy between thermodynamic temperature and that of International Temperature Scale of 1990 (ITS-90)), between 4 K and 305 K have been used by the Working Group for Contact Thermometry of the Consultative Committee for Temperature (CCT-WG-CTh) of the *Bureau International des Poids et Mesures* (BIPM) to produce an analytic function for the difference $T-T_{90}$ as a function of the measured scale temperature T_{90} [1]. This was done so that, in principle, using a thermometer calibrated against ITS-90 one could obtain thermodynamic temperature T without recourse to the expense and inconvenience of primary thermometry. A major challenge for the range 5 K to 24.6 K (the neon triple point) is the dearth of constant-volume gas thermometers, upon which the ITS is defined. To date, accurate measurements of T and thereby $T-T_{90}$ have been performed for temperatures below 25 K using several gas thermometry techniques, namely acoustic gas thermometry (AGT) [2], dielectric-constant gas thermometry (DCGT) [3] and refractive-index gas thermometry (RIGT) [4-6].

In previous work [4], we used single pressure refractive-index gas thermometry (SPRIGT) with ^4He to measure T . Using resistance thermometers calibrated against T_{90} , we determined values of the difference $T-T_{90}$. The values obtained for T at temperatures from 5 K to 24.6 K had standard uncertainties $u(T)$ below 0.17 mK, slightly better than those obtained with AGT and DCGT. At this level of performance, the instrument can be used not only for research but also to calibrate transfer standard thermometers. These calibrated thermometers will be used in turn to carry out international comparisons of T_{90} and T .

Although most of the ITS-90 was based on the use of Pt resistance thermometers [7], at temperatures below 13.8 K (the hydrogen triple point), such devices are too insensitive to be useful. For the range 5 K to 24.6 K, highly stable rhodium-iron (RIRT) or platinum-cobalt resistance thermometers (PtCo) are used instead [8-10]. Before any of these comparisons can be made, however, it is vital to check the reproducibility of the results over a period of several years. This was the aim of the present work.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. In section 2 we briefly describe the apparatus and experimental procedure [11]. Section 3 deals with the results including new measurements of T and T_{90} . In Section 4 we describe direct calibration of resistance thermometers against thermodynamic temperature using SPRIGT. The same

section presents a comparison of two calibrations performed 30 months apart, the latter after nine temperature cycles of whole system between 4 K and room temperature. A conclusion and perspectives in section 5 round off the paper.

2 Apparatus and experimental procedure

The present work is essentially a careful repeat experiment of our previous one [4] by using a new experimental procedure of Constant Refractive-Index Gas Thermometry (CRIGT) [11]. Although only very minor modifications were made to the apparatus, the data acquisition schema and analysis were refined. The experimental apparatus used in the present study is the same as that of our previous work [4], *i.e.*, Single-Pressure Refractive-Index Gas Thermometry (SPRIGT). The system is mainly composed of three subsystems: one for temperature control [12-14], another for pressure control and measurement [15] (the gas handling sub-system), and a third for microwave resonance frequency measurement [16]. The working principle, calculation methods and experimental apparatus of SPRIGT have all been described in detail in reference [4].

Between our previous measurement (hereafter called Run 10) and the present one (Run 19), the system was opened and closed several times for minor improvements and maintenance.

2.1 New CRIGT procedure

Once the controlled temperature and helium-4 gaseous pressure inside the microwave resonator are stable enough, with a typical absolute temperature stability of 10 μ K and a relative pressure stability of 0.3 ppm, microwave measurements were carried out. In contrast to Run10 where only three resonator modes were used (TM11, TE11 and TE13), in Run 19, six modes were employed (TM11, TE11, TE12, TM13, TE13 and TE14). To speed up data acquisition, measurements were implemented, at four isobars from 120 kPa down to 30 kPa. In Run 10, the values chosen for pressure and temperature were somewhat arbitrary. Here, however, a new strategy was implemented, namely constant-refractive-index gas thermometry (CRIGT) which enables measurements at *constant microwave frequency* [11]. By keeping the frequency constant, we avoid potential issues such as variable impedance matching. With this method, values of pressure constraint the temperature. To a first approximation, the ratio of the temperature T to the reference temperature T_{ref} should be the same as that of the pressure p to the pressure at the reference temperature p_{ref} . This choice led to the set of pressure and temperatures shown in Table 1. As for the temperature reference used in SPRIGT, we used a platinum-cobalt thermometer calibrated in France near the

neon triple point using AGT [2], denoted as T_{AGT} .

Table 1. Values of pressure and temperature used in the present work. Each column denotes approximately constant-pressure SPRIGT measurements, while each row refers to ones made at approximately constant refractive-index RIGT (CRIGT), the results of which will be discussed elsewhere [11]. T_{AGT} is the reference temperature, cl. Missing values denote temperatures beyond the reach of our present apparatus.

Refractive-Index \ Pressure		<i>SPRIGT method</i>			
		120 kPa	90 kPa	60 kPa	30 kPa
<i>CRIGT method</i>	Constant n_1	$T_{\text{ref}} = T_{\text{AGT}}$	18.47 K	12.39 K	6.31 K
	Constant n_2	20.26 K	15.27 K	10.27 K	5.28 K
	Constant n_3	10.00 K	7.64 K	5.29 K	/
	Constant n_4	/	$T_{\text{ref}} = T_{\text{AGT}}$	16.42 K	8.30 K
	Constant n_5	/	10.00 K	6.81 K	/
	Constant n_6	/	/	$T_{\text{ref}} = T_{\text{AGT}}$	12.33 K
	Constant n_7	/	/	/	$T_{\text{ref}} = T_{\text{AGT}}$

2.2 Experimental elements

For pressure control and measurement, we used the same components as in our previous work[4, 15], including the same working gas ^4He (high purity >99.9999%, bottles from Air Liquide N° 1151147 and N° 1261172). For more detailed information see reference [4]. For the analysis we used the same values for the virial coefficients of ^4He , i.e., B [17], C [18], D [19], A_ε [20], B_ε [21], C_ε [22-26], A_μ [27], and the isothermal compressibility k_T [28]. For temperature and microwave measurements, however, some components were changed, as shown in Table 2.

2.2.1 Reference temperature

In the present work, the reference thermodynamic temperatures T_{ref} were directly reproduced at the calibrated temperature T_{Ne} measured by AGT[2] with an offset of only 13 μK . Including the calibration uncertainty of the reference (160 μK), and reproducibility (60 μK) the total standard uncertainties of the reference temperature T_{ref} for 30 kPa, 60 kPa, 90 kPa and 120 kPa, come to 170 μK . The uncertainty contribution from the sensitivity S of the PtCo resistance thermometer amounted to a mere 0.03 μK .

2.2.2 Temperature control

The description of our cryostat used to cool the resonator was presented in

references [12, 13], in which the temperature control on the second flange was also described in detailed. Here we only present the temperature control on the microwave resonator.

In the present work, the fully calibrated RIRT (Tinsley type) used to control the resonator temperature was replaced by a $53\ \Omega$ resistance thermometer of the same type of known. The RIRT was manufactured recently by TIPC-CAS and Kun-ming Dafang Science and Technology Ltd, China. It was calibrated by *Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica* (INRiM), Italy at the triple points of neon (24.5561 K) and water (273.16 K), and is denoted here by RIRT_INRiM2.

2.2.3 Temperature T_{90} measurements

In the present work, the best estimate of T_{90} , hereafter referred to as $T_{90,CAS}$, is the same as that used in our previous thermometry campaign [4]. It corresponds to the weighted mean values of the readings of three RIRTs. RIRT_NPL1 (Tinsley type, SN 226242) and RIRT_NPL3 (Tinsley type, SN 226950) were calibrated by NPL UK, while RIRT_NIST (TIPC-CAS and Kun-ming Dafang Science and Technology Ltd., SN 20107) was calibrated by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), Gaithersburg USA. For detailed information on this subject see reference [4]. The only difference is that the two $10\ \Omega$ standard resistors, Tinsley 5685A SN 7800BP0 and SN 1580409, used for measuring resistances of the three RIRT were replaced with new ones, WIKA 5685A SN 045068-01 and SN 045068-02 respectively.

2.2.4 Microwave measurements

In the present work, the 10 MHz rubidium frequency reference for microwave measurements was changed from a Stanford Research Systems model FS725 [4] to a model FS740 since the latter could be locked to a GPS signal captured by an outdoor antenna. Moreover, in the present work, two 10 dBm amplifiers (Mini-Circuits model ZX60-14012L-S+, bandwidth from 0.3 MHz to 14 GHz) were used to increase the stability and resolution of microwave resonance frequency [29]. Furthermore, six microwave modes, TM11, TE11, TE12, TM12, TE13 and TE14, were employed instead of three previously so as to boost confidence in the determined thermodynamic temperature.

Table 2. Differences between apparatus used for temperature measurements in this work and our previous SPRIGT work[4].

Measurement and control components		Previous SPRIGT work[4]	This work
Reference temperature	Values	Lower than the calibrated temperature T_{AGT} [2] about 0.24 mK [30]	Reproduced at the calibrated temperature T_{AGT} [2] to within 13 μ K
Temperature control	RIRT thermometer	100 Ω NPL2 (Tinsley, SN 226245), mounted in lower hemisphere	53 Ω INRiM2 (TIPC-CAS and Kun-ming Dafang Science and Technology Ltd., SN LT002) mounted in upper hemisphere
	10 Ω Standard resistor	Tinsley 5685A, SN 1631808	WIKA (formerly ASL) 5685A, SN 045068-03
T_{90} measurements	10 Ω Standard resistor	Tinsley 5685A, SN 1580409 Tinsley 5685A, SN 7800BP0	WIKA 5685A, SN 045068-01 WIKA 5685A, SN 045068-02
Microwave measurements	Frequency reference (10 MHz rubidium frequency standard)	Stanford Research Systems FS725	Stanford Research Systems FS740, locked to GPS via an outdoor antenna [16]
	Amplifiers	Not used	Two 10 dBm amplifiers
	Resonator modes	TM11, TE11, TE13	TM11, TE11, TE12, TM13, TE13, TE14

Note: values of all the 10 Ω standard resistors used were traced back to National Institute of Metrology (NIM) China.

3 Results and discussion

Based on the working equations of thermodynamic temperature and uncertainty calculation of SPRIGT in our previous work [4], i.e., sections 1.2 and 5.1, a new thermodynamic temperature T and difference $T-T_{90}$ data were determined in this work run 19.

3.1 Temperature control

The temperature of the resonator, monitored by RIRT_NPL1 with the help of the WIKA F900 AC resistance bridge and a WIKA 5685A 10 Ω standard resistors (SN 045068-01), were controlled with stabilities all below 20 μK , see Figure 1. The temperature stabilities of the resonator are somewhat larger than those of about 10 μK in our previous work [4, 14]. This is because the sensitivity of the present control resistance thermometer, 53 Ω RIRT_INRiM2, is lower than that of the 100 Ω RIRT_NPL2 used previously, so it has a lower temperature resolution, making it less suitable for temperature control [14].

Figure 1. Temperature stability of the microwave resonator at four different pressures for temperatures from 5 K to 24.6 K.

3.2 T_{90} measurement

By weighting the readings of the three RIRTs, we determined $T_{90,\text{CAS}}$ at temperatures from 5 K to 25 K with uncertainties below 0.22 mK. Figure 2 shows a plot of the differences of $T_{90,\text{CAS}}$, $\Delta T_{90,\text{CAS}}$ defined in equation (1), determined in this work (Run 19) and our previous work (Run 10) [4]. We find almost all values of $\Delta T_{90,\text{CAS}}$ lie within ± 20 μK of each other, except for two points distant by no more than 60 μK . These $T_{90,\text{CAS}}$ differences are consistent with its standard deviation of 30 μK , as

shown in Figure 15 of our previous article on the subject [4]. The results demonstrate that the system has a good repeatability for $T_{90,CAS}$ measurements performed 2.5 years apart.

$$\Delta T_{90,CAS} = T_{90,CAS}^{\text{Run 19}} - T_{90,CAS}^{\text{Run 10}} \quad (1)$$

Figure 2. Differences of $T_{90,CAS}$ between Run 10 [4] and Run 19 at temperatures from 5 K to 24.6 K. In the whole range, the mean value of $\Delta T_{90,CAS}$ is $-9.4 \mu\text{K}$ and standard deviation of that is $21 \mu\text{K}$ shown in the shaded area.

3.3 Pressure control and measurement

In this work, relative pressure stabilities better than 0.35 ppm were achieved under pressures of 30 kPa, 60 kPa, 90 kPa and 120 kPa at temperatures from 5 K to 24.6 K using the same control and measuring methods in our previous work [4]. The results are plotted in Figure 3. These stabilities are slightly poorer than those of better than 0.16 ppm in [4]. The main reason is that the interaction between gas pressure control and temperature control, the standard deviation of temperature fluctuations, $20 \mu\text{K}$, being twice as high as in our earlier work [4]. This highlights the need to control resonator temperature very well to achieve a stable gas internal pressure. For absolute pressure measurements, typical standard uncertainties of 6.2 ppm, 5.6 ppm, 5.4 ppm and 5.3 ppm were obtained respectively at measured pressures of 30 kPa, 60 kPa, 90 kPa and 120 kPa, which are comparable with those values given in our previous publication [4].

Figure 3. Relative pressure stability for four isobars at temperatures from 5 K to 24.6 K.

3.4 Microwave resonance frequency measurement

Figure 4 shows a plot of thermodynamic temperature uncertainty component, mode consistency $u(T_{\text{mode}})$, estimated from the standard deviation of T determined from the six microwave modes. The values of $u(T_{\text{mode}})$ never exceeds 85 μK , which is comparable with values of less than 70 μK obtained in our earlier experiment [4] using only three microwave modes: TM11, TE11 and TE13. This enhances our confidence in the conclusion on the repeatability of T in the present work. Furthermore, the uncertainty contribution from the microwave resonance frequency, u_f , is no longer a major factor for $u(T)$, given the higher stability and improved resolution of microwave resonance frequency in the present work. This is because with the help of two amplifiers the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the peaks of the microwave resonator was increased 11-fold¹, which in turn increased the resonance frequency measurement resolution 11 times, as shown in Figure 5 for TM11 microwave mode.

¹ The typical values of SNR for microwave measurements without and with the two amplifiers were 3300 and 36500 respectively at temperatures from 5 K to 25 K.

Figure 4. Mode consistency $u(T_{\text{mode}})$ estimated from T determined using the six microwave modes at four isobars by SPRIGT for temperatures from 5 K to 24.6 K.

Figure 5. Modulus of scattering parameter $|S_{21}|$ amplitude of TM11 versus microwave frequency without and with the two microwave amplifiers at 24.6 K.

3.5 $T-T_{90}$ results

Table 3 lists the new data of $T-T_{90}$ obtained in this work. Over the whole temperature range, 5 K - 24.6 K, the uncertainty in T , $u(T)$, is better than 0.17 mK, as was the case in our original experiment [30] (refer to Table 9). Figure 6 and Figure 7 show a comparison of results for $T-T_{90}$ determined in this work (Run 19) and in our previous measurement (Run 10) [30]. The $T-T_{90}$ results for the two independent runs, Run 10 and Run 19, show good agreement with differences all within their standard uncertainties. The differences in $T-T_{90}$ between the two runs are defined as in equation (2). They lie below 70 μK with a maximum value less than 100 μK , equivalent to 0.9 times its standard uncertainty. The reproducibility of $T-T_{90}$ over the whole range is 35 μK , whereas that for $T_{90,\text{cas}}$ is 21 μK . Using quadratic subtraction of these values, we estimated the reproducibility of T_{SPRIGT} over the whole range to be 28 μK .

$$\Delta(T_{\text{SPRIGT}} - T_{90,\text{CAS}}) = (T_{\text{SPRIGT}} - T_{90,\text{CAS}})^{\text{Run19}} - (T_{\text{SPRIGT}} - T_{90,\text{CAS}})^{\text{Run10}} \quad (2)$$

From these comparison results of $T-T_{90}$ and others key parameters presented above in sections 3.1-3.4, we conclude that the SPRIGT system is remained stable over 2.5 years even though many measurement and control components were replaced compared with our previous experimental set-up [4], as already shown in Table 2.

Figure 6. Comparison of $T-T_{90}$ results of two runs performed 2.5 years apart. Thick line: $T-T_{90,CAS}$ determined in our previous work [30](Table 9, Run10); thin lines: standard uncertainty of $T-T_{90,CAS}$, $u(T-T_{90,CAS})$. Symbols and error bars: $T-T_{90,CAS}$ and $u(T-T_{90,CAS})$ determined in this work (Run19) at 30 kPa, 60 kPa, 90 kPa and 120 kPa.

Figure 7. Difference of $T-T_{90}$ measured by SPRIGT between Run 10 [30] and Run 19. In the whole range, the mean value of $\Delta(T_{SPRIGT}-T_{90,CAS})$ is 31 μ K and standard deviation of that is 35 μ K shown in the shaded area.

Table 3. New $T - T_{90,CAS}$ data for temperatures from 5 K to 24.6 K determined by SPRIGT, Run 19.

No.	T	$u(T)$	$T_{90,CAS}$	$u(T_{90,CAS})$	$T-T_{90,CAS}$	$u(T-T_{90,CAS})$
	K	mK	K	mK	mK	mK
1	24.55498 ¹	0.17 ²	24.55532	0.21	-0.34	0.27
2	20.26792	0.13	20.26762	0.17	0.30	0.21
3	18.47507	0.11	18.47440	0.19	0.67	0.22
4	16.42947	0.09	16.42868	0.22	0.79	0.24
5	15.27259	0.10	15.27175	0.14	0.84	0.18

6	12.39586	0.08	12.39544	0.13	0.42	0.15
7	12.33810	0.08	12.33771	0.13	0.39	0.16
8	10.27767	0.08	10.27738	0.13	0.29	0.15
9	10.00097 ³	0.11 ⁴	10.00068	0.13	0.29	0.17
10	8.30501	0.06	8.30467	0.12	0.34	0.13
11	7.64766	0.10	7.64733	0.11	0.33	0.15
12	6.81500	0.08	6.81458	0.11	0.42	0.13
13	6.31740	0.05	6.31694	0.11	0.46	0.12
14	5.29524	0.10	5.29479	0.11	0.45	0.15
15	5.28348	0.05	5.28301	0.11	0.47	0.12

¹ Averaged over four pressures 30 kPa, 60 kPa, 90 kPa and 120 kPa at the reference points.

² Including an additional uncertainty component of 0.005 mK from average T .

³ Averaged over two pressures 90 kPa and 120 kPa at the same temperature 10 K.

⁴ Including an additional uncertainty component of 0.015 mK from average T .

4 Applications of the thermodynamic temperature T_{SPRIGT}

To disseminate thermodynamic temperature T , one can transfer it to other devices by calibrating highly stable resistance thermometers, i.e., building a wire scale carrying the relationship between temperature T and resistance R . This was what was done in the present work.

4.1 Data processing

Once the temperature and pressure were stable enough, the thermodynamic temperature experiment of SPRIGT was carried out in two steps.

In the first step, measurements were performed with the resonator under vacuum. RIRT_NPL1 was used as the reference thermometer for T_{90} and its resistance measured continuously with the WIKA F900 bridge. The WIKA F18 bridge was used to measure the resistances of the other thermometer, usually RIRT_NPL3 or RIRT_NIST. A manual scan procedure was implemented, following the sequence shown in reference [4], which included measurements of self-heating. After this, the temperatures T'_{90} and zero-current resistances R'_0 of the thermometers were determined.

In Step 2, thermodynamic temperature measurements were carried out under pressures of 30 kPa, 60 kPa, 90 kPa and 120 kPa. The temperatures T_{90} and zero-current resistances R_0 of RIRT_NPL1 and RIRT_NPL3 were once again recorded simultaneously with T . Usually there was a smaller temperature difference of RIRT_NPL1 compared with that of the resistances held under vacuum, typically about 30 μK , since sometimes the temperature control set points drifted due to the reduced self-heating of RIRT_NPL1 under pressure [4].

To build as accurate a wire scale as possible for thermodynamic temperature

T_{SPRIGT} , it was necessary to apply a small correction in order to ensure that all three RIRTs readings corresponded to a given thermodynamic temperature T . To this end, the correction, denoted here by δT_{90} , defined in [equation \(3\)](#) using NPL1 as a reference, was calculated for the other two thermometers using [equation \(4\)](#) to according for the temperature change from thermodynamic state of Step 1 against that of Step 2 with T measurements.

$$\delta T_{90} \equiv T_{90, \text{NPL1}} - T'_{90, \text{NPL1}} = (R_{0, \text{NPL1}} - R'_{0, \text{NPL1}}) \cdot \left(\frac{dR}{dT_{90}} \Big|_{T_{90}=T'_{90, \text{NPL1}}} \right)^{-1} \quad (3)$$

where dR/dT is the sensitivity of the RIRT. We remind the reader that the prime refers to measurements made under vacuum.

The correction of temperature difference δT_{90} used here follows that in CCT Key Comparison No 1 (CCT-K1) [8]. δT_{90} has the same value for the three RIRTs at the equivalent temperatures, since the temperatures in the two Steps, under vacuum and pressures, generally differed by only a few of microkelvin, no more than 30 μK (see [Figure 17](#) in our reference [4]).

$$T_{90, \text{NPL3}} - T'_{90, \text{NPL3}} = T_{90, \text{NIST}} - T'_{90, \text{NIST}} = \delta T_{90} \quad (4)$$

Similar to [equation \(3\)](#), zero-current resistances R_0 of RIRT_NPL3 and RIRT_NIST in Step 1 and Step 2 can be written as follows:

$$T_{90, \text{NPL3}} - T'_{90, \text{NPL3}} = (R_{0, \text{NPL3}} - R'_{0, \text{NPL3}}) \cdot \left(\frac{dR}{dT_{90}} \Big|_{T_{90}=T'_{90, \text{NPL3}}} \right)^{-1} \quad (5)$$

$$T_{90, \text{NIST}} - T'_{90, \text{NIST}} = (R_{0, \text{NIST}} - R'_{0, \text{NIST}}) \cdot \left(\frac{dR}{dT_{90}} \Big|_{T_{90}=T'_{90, \text{NIST}}} \right)^{-1} \quad (6)$$

Using [equations \(3\)](#) to [\(6\)](#), zero-current resistances R_0 of RIRT_NPL3 and RIRT_NIST in Step 2 were determined respectively by the following two equations

$$R_{0, \text{NPL3}} = R'_{0, \text{NPL3}} + (R_{0, \text{NPL1}} - R'_{0, \text{NPL1}}) \cdot \left(\frac{dR}{dT_{90}} \Big|_{T_{90}=T'_{90, \text{NPL3}}} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{dR}{dT_{90}} \Big|_{T_{90}=T'_{90, \text{NPL1}}} \right)^{-1} \quad (7)$$

$$R_{0, \text{NIST}} = R'_{0, \text{NIST}} + (R_{0, \text{NPL1}} - R'_{0, \text{NPL1}}) \cdot \left(\frac{dR}{dT_{90}} \Big|_{T_{90}=T'_{90, \text{NIST}}} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{dR}{dT_{90}} \Big|_{T_{90}=T'_{90, \text{NPL1}}} \right)^{-1} \quad (8)$$

[Table 4](#) lists the experimental data sets of the determined thermodynamic temperature T_{SPRIGT} and corresponding zero-current resistances R_0 of the three RIRTs, namely RIRT_NPL1 (SN 226242), RIRT_NPL3 (SN 226950) and RIRT_NIST (SN 20107), in our previous work [4, 30] (Run 10) and the more recent measurement

(Run 19). Later we shall transpose T_{SPRIGT} to other highly stable low-temperature thermometers by directly reproducing the values of the corresponding zero-current resistances R_0 of the three RIRTs listed in [Table 4](#). In addition, these resistances will be used to build a wire scale for thermodynamic temperature T_{Scale} . We shall do this by obtaining the relationship between T_{SPRIGT} and R_0 for the three RIRTs, as described in the next section.

Table 4. Thermodynamic temperature T_{SPRIGT} and corresponding zero-current resistances R_0 of the three RIRTs, namely RIRT_NPL1 (SN 226242), RIRT_NPL3 (SN 226950) and RIRT_NIST (SN 20107), determined in our first campaign [4, 30] (Run 10) and in this recent work (Run 19).

No.	T_{SPRIGT}	$u(T_{\text{SPRIGT}})$	RIRT_NPL1 (SN 226242)		RIRT_NPL3 (SN 226950)		RIRT_NIST (SN 20107)	
			R_0	$u(R_0)$	R_0	$u(R_0)$	R_0	$u(R_0)$
/	K	mK	Ω	Ω	Ω	Ω	Ω	Ω
1	24.55535 ¹	0.16	11.0659344	0.0000052	12.8351694	0.0000054	4.8806154	0.0000020
2	24.55498 ²	0.17	11.0658836	0.0000062	12.8351114	0.0000059	4.8805949	0.0000020
3	23.00025 ¹	0.15	10.8457923	0.0000041	12.5904187	0.0000060	4.7835131	0.0000021
4	21.99973 ¹	0.13	10.7004675	0.0000035	12.4286150	0.0000069	4.7193207	0.0000027
5	20.99829 ¹	0.12	10.5511443	0.0000033	12.2622101	0.0000037	4.6533036	0.0000018
6	20.26791 ³	0.12	10.4393131	0.0000057	12.1375087	0.0000061	4.6038320	0.0000029
7	18.99873 ¹	0.10	10.2379439	0.0000035	11.9128449	0.0000040	4.5147053	0.0000018
8	18.47507 ²	0.11	10.1518911	0.0000060	11.8167985	0.0000048	4.4766061	0.0000022
9	17.99978 ¹	0.10	10.0721080	0.0000043	11.7277480	0.0000043	4.4412764	0.0000027
10	17.03389 ¹	0.09	9.9045831	0.0000033	11.5407251	0.0000038	4.3670855	0.0000016
11	16.42947 ²	0.09	9.7957311	0.0000039	11.4191937	0.0000058	4.3188744	0.0000059
12	16.00012 ¹	0.08	9.7163568	0.0000039	11.3305706	0.0000046	4.2837198	0.0000025
13	15.27259 ²	0.10	9.5776793	0.0000070	11.1757349	0.0000067	4.2223019	0.0000038
14	15.00062 ¹	0.07	9.5244079	0.0000044	11.1162626	0.0000059	4.1987085	0.0000020
15	13.80428 ¹	0.07	9.2799572	0.0000046	10.8433652	0.0000041	4.0904592	0.0000021
16	12.39586 ²	0.08	8.9684064	0.0000057	10.4956403	0.0000092	3.9525348	0.0000059
17	12.33810 ²	0.08	8.9550238	0.0000033	10.4807063	0.0000075	3.9466108	0.0000027
18	12.00053 ¹	0.06	8.8757467	0.0000077	10.3922485	0.0000078	3.9115227	0.0000033
19	10.27767 ²	0.08	8.4410564	0.0000041	9.907313	0.000018	3.7191912	0.0000059
20	10.00096 ³	0.08	8.3660647	0.0000088	9.823671	0.000017	3.6860195	0.0000060
21	8.30501 ²	0.06	7.8696160	0.0000036	9.270111	0.000022	3.4665013	0.0000069
22	8.00098 ¹	0.05	7.7732220	0.0000066	9.162637	0.000011	3.4238864	0.0000032
23	7.64766 ²	0.10	7.658042	0.000014	9.034237	0.000015	3.3729763	0.0000069
24	7.00026 ¹	0.05	7.4376787	0.0000048	8.7885711	0.0000063	3.2755783	0.0000024
25	6.81500 ²	0.08	7.3722577	0.0000097	8.715640	0.000014	3.246665	0.0000016
26	6.31740 ²	0.05	7.1910992	0.000018	8.513671	0.000016	3.1665962	0.0000065
27	6.00007 ¹	0.05	7.0712117	0.0000057	8.379995	0.000013	3.1136138	0.0000047
28	5.29524 ²	0.10	6.791831	0.000022	8.068394	0.000015	2.9901143	0.0000018
29	5.28348 ²	0.05	6.786996	0.000022	8.063001	0.000015	2.9879763	0.0000018
30	5.00021 ¹	0.06	6.6692587	0.0000053	7.9316376	0.0000064	2.9359133	0.0000026

¹ Experimental data from our previous work (Run 10) [30].

² Experimental data in the present work (Run 19).

³ Average of two temperatures determined in Run 10 and Run 19 which differ by only 20 μK .

4.2 Wire scale of thermodynamic temperature T_{SPRIGT}

Using data in [Table 4](#), we established a wire scale for thermodynamic temperature T_{SPRIGT} by transferring T_{SPRIGT} to zero-current resistances R_0 of RIRT_NPL1 (SN 226242), RIRT_NPL3 (SN 226950) and RIRT_NIST (SN 20107). The relationship between T_{SPRIGT} and R_0 for each RIRT was determined by a 9-parameter polynomial defined by

$$T_{\text{Scale}} / \text{K} = \sum_{l=0}^7 b_l x^l + b_8 x^9 \quad (9)$$

where

$$x = \frac{2R_0 - R_{0,\text{max}} - R_{0,\text{min}}}{R_{0,\text{max}} - R_{0,\text{min}}}. \quad (10)$$

where x is the normalized zero-current resistance, $R_{0,\text{max}}$ and $R_{0,\text{min}}$ means the maximal and minimal zero-current resistance of the three RIRTs listed in [Table 5](#), which correspond to the maximal and minimal T_{SPRIGT} .

The fitting procedure minimizes the sum of the squared temperature difference

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^N \left[(T_{\text{SPRIGT}} - T_{\text{Scale}})_i / \text{mK} \right]^2 \quad (11)$$

where N is the total number of experimental data points. The values in [Table 4](#) have been provided should the interested reader wish to fit data with a different function, for whatever reason, be it now or at a future date.

To reproduce T_{SPRIGT} better, we compared unweighted and weighted least-squares fits. However, we found that using one or other type of fitting procedure makes almost no difference to the uncertainty in T . Finally, unweighted least squares fitting was chosen and carried out with the objective function of [equation \(11\)](#). The fitting coefficients in [equation \(9\)](#) are listed in [Table 5](#) for the three RIRTs, based upon which a wire scale of thermodynamic temperature T_{Scale} under the new SI was built from 5 K to 24.6 K. The wire scale can be used to interpolate T_{SPRIGT} from a zero-current resistance R_0 of three RIRTs.

Table 5. Coefficients in equations (9) and (10) for RIRT_NPL1 (SN 226242), RIRT_NPL3 (SN 226950) and RIRT_NIST (SN 20107) for a thermodynamic temperature wire scale from 5 K to 24.6 K.

l	RIRT_NPL1 (SN 226242)	RIRT_NPL3 (SN 226950)	RIRT_NIST (SN 20107)
	b_l		
0	11.9662535	11.9672172	11.9695713
1	9.2351213	9.2312577	9.2317134
2	2.8736804	2.8603251	2.8583188
3	0.6879851	0.6810861	0.6812197
4	0.0648149	0.0707773	0.0702691
5	-0.0706226	-0.0630688	-0.0650968
6	-0.1270044	-0.1205578	-0.1204104
7	-0.0976355	-0.0924025	-0.0897862
8	0.0227359	0.0207058	0.0195197
$R_{0, \max} / \Omega$	11.0659344	12.8351694	4.8806154
$R_{0, \min} / \Omega$	6.6692587	7.9316376	2.9359133

Figure 8 shows the fitting residual results for the thermodynamic temperature wire scale in equation (9) for the three RIRTs, for the temperature range 5 K to 24.6 K. It is clear that T_{Scale} and T_{SPRIGT} show good mutual agreement over the whole temperature range with all deviations lying within the standard uncertainty of T_{Scale} , $u(T_{\text{Scale}})$. The standard deviations of the fitting residual are 39 μK , 32 μK and 34 μK for RIRT_NPL, RIRT_NPL3 and RIRT_NIST respectively, the average value of which is 35 μK . This is consistent with the reproducibility of T_{SPRIGT} with a value of 28 μK estimated in section 3.5.

Figure 8. Fitting residuals for the thermodynamic temperature wire scale T_{Scale} (equation (9)) by RIRT_NPL1 (SN 226242), RIRT_NPL3 (SN 226950) and RIRT_NIST (SN 20107) for at temperatures ranging from 5 K to 24.6 K.

As for the estimation of $u(T_{\text{Scale}})$, three parts were considered, namely measured

$u(T_{\text{SPRIGT}})^2$ with values in Table 4, the average value of standard deviations of fitting residuals for the three RIRTs with a value of 35 μK , and the long-term stability of the three RIRTs with a value of 30 μK (see figure 15 in reference [4]). In our estimation, the three uncertainty components of $u(T_{\text{Scale}})$ were supposed to be independent and used to calculate $u(T_{\text{Scale}})$. Subsequently, for convenience, $u(T_{\text{Scale}})$ was obtained as a function of T_{Scale} by fitting a second-order polynomial given by equation (12); the standard deviation of the fitting residuals was 13 μK .

$$u(T_{\text{Scale}}) / \text{mK} = 0.09860 - 0.00477 \times (T_{\text{Scale}} / \text{K}) + 0.00031 \times (T_{\text{Scale}} / \text{K})^2 \quad (12)$$

To date, a thermodynamic temperature wire scale T_{Scale} has been firstly established for temperatures from 5 K to 24.6 K under new SI with uncertainty better than 0.2mK based on 30 experimental data points of SPRIGT. Later we shall transpose this T_{Scale} to other rhodium-iron thermometers and platinum-cobalt resistance thermometers. Thereafter, these calibrated thermometers could be used either as local temperature standards or else as transfer standards in an international comparison of thermodynamic temperature below 25 K.

5 Conclusion and perspectives

The present work aimed to check reproducibility and stability of SPRIGT by implementing a new CRIGT measurement produce, and if they were good enough, disseminate thermodynamic temperature by establishing a wire scale for thermodynamic temperature as defined by the new SI. Following improvements and other modifications to the SPRIGT apparatus, new data of $T-T_{90}$ were acquired for the range 5 K to 24.6 K, using gaseous ^4He at pressures from 30 kPa to 120 kPa.

A detailed comparison was made directly between the present work (Run 19) and our earlier measurements (Run 10) [4]. The SPRIGT systems show good repeatability for temperature, pressure control and microwave measurements with comparable values of absolute temperature stability, relative pressure stability and pressure measurement uncertainty, and mode consistency of thermodynamic temperature. As before, the uncertainty in T is better than 0.17 mK. Moreover, good agreement of $T_{90,\text{CAS}}$ and $T-T_{90,\text{CAS}}$ was also observed. The differences $\Delta T_{90,\text{CAS}}$ never exceed 60 μK , while the differences $\Delta(T-T_{90,\text{CAS}})$ are no more than 100 μK , equivalent to 0.9 times the standard uncertainty. The reproducibilities of $T_{90,\text{CAS}}$, T and $T-T_{90}$ are 21 μK , 28 μK and 35 μK respectively over the whole temperature range. The results demonstrate a

² To be simple here the experimental $u(T_{\text{SPRIGT}})$ was used, since it is usually larger than the fitted uncertainty $u_{\text{fit}}(T_{\text{SPRIGT}})$, which can be estimated by Monte Carlo simulation.

remarkable agreement between two SPRIGT runs performed 2.5 years apart.

This excellent performance increases our confidence to carry out thermometer calibration or international comparison of thermodynamic temperature below 25 K by SPRIGT via highly stable resistance thermometers. In this work, the former has been firstly demonstrated via the setting up of a thermodynamic temperature wire scale under the new SI using three RIRTs with uncertainty better than 0.2mK. It is hoped the latter, i.e., international comparisons with other primary gas thermometry systems, will be implemented within the next few years.

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